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Plot Transformation and Intertextual Effects

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Abstract: *In the article, the principles of character creation and expression of the unique image of heroes in recent years in Uzbek prose, especially in Uzbek novels, have been researched.*

Key words: *image, modification, existentialism, absurdity, hero, personal tragedy.*

In any epic work, the plot occupies a special place in the narrative of events and in the structure of the work of art in general. Although the content of the work of art is relatively variable in each period, the formal aspects and the plot structure change relatively slowly. But it should be taken for granted that the plot of a work of art is presented in different styles. In this regard, literary critic Damin Toraev said in his study "Poetics of Plot in Contemporary Uzbek Prose": "One of the important principles of the development of our national prose in recent years is the widening of the range of topics as a result of the freedom created in the creative process, and the fact that the plot of artistic works is presented in different styles depicting the various psychological experiences of our people,"¹ very aptly point out. Indeed, freedom in creativity had a positive effect on the theme, style and plot. Accordingly, there is a need to examine the nature of the plot of novels from a new perspective today.

Studying prose works on the basis of plot elements, which have been emphasized so far in literary studies, evaluating the modification phenomenon in the plot, and researching the factors of literary influence will help to reveal many artistic features of Isajon Sultan's novels. After all, the construction of the plot in the literary novels is close to each other, and at the same time, compared to the novels "The eternal wanderer" (Boqiy darbadar) and "Independent" (Ozod), the plot structure in the novel "Genetic" is distinguished by its mixed and traditional appearance. The alternation of different plot types in Isajon Sultan's novels, sometimes the author's harmonious use of plot types in his novels, allows us to think about the modification of this theoretical concept.

¹Дамин Тўраев. Ҳозирги ўзбек насрида сюжет поэтикasi/Рангин тасвирлар жилоси. Тошкент. "Akademnashr" нашриёти. 2014 йил, 21-бет.

It is known that Uzbek literary experts have theoretically discussed the literary plots existing in the world literature and highlighted their types such as chronicle plot, concentric plot, retrospective plot, and associative plot.² In novels written on the basis of a chronicle plot, events are told sequentially, according to the passage of years and dates in the life of the central character. It is appropriate to give examples of such novels as Abdulla Kadiri's "The Past Days" (Utkan kunlar), Oibek's "Navoi" (Navoiy), and Pirimkul Kadirov's "Babur" (Bobur). In novels based on a concentric plot, events are connected to each other by some internal cause and effect. In this case, one event requires the other. Ernest Hemingway's novels "The Old Man and the Sea" (Chol va dengiz) and Abdulla Qahhor's "Mirage" (Sarob) are examples of this. If the plot of a prose work is based on retrospection, then in such novels "retreat" and "return" occur. Examples of novels written on the basis of this type of plot are Ch. Aytmatov's "The Day of the Age" (Asrga tatigulik kun), "Doomsday" (Qiyomat), Asqad Mukhtar's "Maple" (Chinor), O'tkir Hashimov's "Between Two Doors" (Ikki eshik orasi). The associative plot system is directly related to spiritual portals, and in such works, the mental experiences that occurred in the nature of the characters as a result of involuntarily fantasizing and remembering something come to the fore. Novels such as "Tulip field" (Iolazor) by Murad Muhammad Dost and "Treasure of Ulugbek" (Ulug'bek xazinasasi) by Odil Yaqubov are examples of this type. While studying the issue of plot modification in Isajon Sultan's novels, the harmony of plot types in his novels is noticeable. In particular, the novel "Genetic" (Genetik) stands out from the attention of this modified harmony. In the description of the events of the novel, even if the narrator narrates the events of the plot line of the work in a chronological manner, he occasionally retreats - he turns to the retrospective direction. There are situations where the plot line of the novel turns in a different direction due to association with a single word or event. In the text of the novel, there are very reasonable and appropriate examples of cases of association by means of a word, event or name. The novel portrays the image of Aunt Sofia, the fate of this woman, the days of her bride, the periods buried in life's worries, as well as her life in old age. In bringing this image between the events, the writer effectively uses the type of imagination, retrospection and association of the plot. Preparing to mention Aunt Sofia in his work, the author writes about the element of nature - the Moon shining in the sky: "Oymomo, whose nights are illuminated over the place, is only the mother of these places. In other places, the Moon does not look like this, they say that my name is not Momo. The Moon rising between the mountains or barren deserts has a completely different appearance. Our own moon is very dear in the nights when the scent of the trees is wafting behind the mulberries and poplars.

When I say repentance, Oy, my aunt Sofia comes to life in my mind. In the end, she was a happy woman with a heart full of light. When I say Aunt Sofia, I think of the wonderful Oymomo who sprinkled rain on the heights"³. In the novel, the characters of Oymomo and Aunt Sofia are depicted side by side. The writer sometimes remembers the moon and compares it to the moon when he wants to portray his hero as a symbol of elegance and innocence. Sometimes in the novel, when thinking about the Moon, it can be understood as Aunt Sofia, and the modification between such an image and the element of nature gives the novel aesthetic beauty and sophistication. The unique image that has mixed with each other attracts the attention of the reader.

In fact, each writer is a unique world, a creator with his own aesthetic image can be influenced by another, but does not repeat it. Various components of the novel also demonstrate the literary and aesthetic principles of this author. Literary scholar Zulfia Pardaeva puts a very appropriate emphasis

²Тўхта Бобоев. "Адабиётшунослик асослари". Тошкент. "Ўқитувчи". 2002 йил 217-бет

³Исажон Султон. Ҳазрати Хизр изидан. Роман, қисса ва ҳикоялар. Фафур Фулом номидаги нашриёт-матбаа ижодий уйи. Тошкент. 2018. 258-бет.

on an important issue specific to the novel: "Another remarkable aspect of the novel genre is that the artistic components specific to the genre appear in each novel in its own way."⁴ In particular, the literary-theoretical components of Isajon Sultan's novels are also unique.

In the novel "Genetic" there is a special section entitled "Aunt Sophia". Naturally, the image or the name of the place, which took place in the plot and composition of the novel, especially in the special title, should be described in more detail in the structure of the novel, and should be carefully connected with the issue at the center of the work. Such a poetic method exists in the history of world literature and Uzbek novels. For example, Mikhail Bulgakov in the first part of his novel "The Master and Margarita" (Мастер и Маргарита) brings out "Понтий Пилат" and in the second part "Margarita" inside a small title. In the novel, both characters are sufficiently described. At the same time, the events take place with the participation of those characters or in their psychological environment. Abdulla Qadiri's novel "The Past days" has chapters such as "Otabek Yusufbek Haji Oglu", "Yusufbek Haji", "Khushruiyibi and Zaynab". In the novel "Starry Nights" (Yulduzli tunlar) by Pirmkul Kadirov, the seasons are named directly by the names of places in the style of "Kuva", "Samarkand", "Kabul", and they are also divided into chapters with numbers. Accordingly, certain chapters in the novel "Genetic" are named as "Aunt Sofia", "Uncle Ubay", "Dost", "Teacher". When thinking about such elements, it becomes clear that Isajon Sultan carefully studied world novels and especially the experiences of Uzbek writers who were his mentors. In fact, any person or place in the title must have some function in the plot of the novel. From this point of view, the image of Aunt Sofia, who plays the main role in the plot of the novel, is given in more detail in the chapter "Aunt Sofia": "Aunt Sofia was a village woman who married without knowing her memory. When I remember, she became a big wife, after her first marriage broke up and her husband kicked her out because she gave birth to a daughter, after some time, she married another man who was much older" (The same source, pp. 264-265). Each image included in the novel should have its own image, attract the reader's attention and, in general, help the creator's ideological position. In "Genetic", the purpose of describing the lifestyle of aunt Sofiya, looking at the paths of life, is to describe the worries of an Uzbek woman in the recent past, her life spent in uniformity. At this time, it was also important for the writer to describe how hard a person's life was spent. The writer who connected the name Sofia to Oymomo, completes the fate of this woman. "My aunt Sofia was a pious and pure woman. I used to go to play with him. When I went, he would immediately set the table, prepare sugar and soup. "My nephew came to see me," he said happily. There was a big mulberry tree in my aunt's yard, sparrows had built nests in its branches, and we were interested in picking its pods. But we were afraid to go to the top, because there is a big snake. It was even more interesting to see the snake, we couldn't get close to the mulberry tree, we watched from a distance to see if it wrapped itself in its branches" (The same source, p. 259). Aunt Sofia's childhood helps the writer to remember the innocent feelings of childhood and the sweet moments that remain in his mind.

As the hero of the novel remembers and describes his experiences, he does not forget his aunt Sofia even after growing up. He goes to him, meets and talks with him. In this, the life path of the hero is given sequentially, befitting a plot based on a chronicle. But the reason for giving it in this sequence is, of course, that the name Sofia reminds of the Moon - the association of this pair. "It was surprising that my aunt's name was not the same as other women's names. The names of the women in our village are Oyniso, Turgunniso, Khosiyat, Nazira, Ibodat... and my grandmother, who spent her life farming in the field, has no idea about such a name. Of course, I didn't even know the meaning. Because "ay" or

⁴З.Пардаева. Ўзбек романи поэтикаси (Ҳозирги ўзбек романларининг таҳлили мисолида). Тошкент. Абдулла Қодирий номидаги халқ мероси нашриёти. 2003 йил. 9-бет.

"khan" is added to a woman's name, everyone called my aunt "Sofiya Khan" or "Sofiyaoy", in the village language it had already changed to "Sapiya". I like the name Sofia more because it reminds me of the imaginary full moon seen through the night clouds"⁵. Apart from the sight of the moon, Aunt Sofia has already seen the moon in her dreams. By the way, if a person doesn't know the meaning of his name, when the meaning of his name is explained to him, his eyes will be happy and he will be very satisfied. So what does "Sofia" mean? "When I grew up, my aunt became an old woman. I still miss that light, those faces. Sometimes, at night, I suddenly have visions. I like the soft smile, the purity and purity of the face.

When I grew up, I learned the meaning of that name. When I learned that "Sophia" means "divine wisdom" in Greek and "purity" in Arabic, I thought, "Of course, I will tell my aunt, she will be happy to hear." At that time, my aunt's love for me grew even more, she used to say "my wrestler boy" (The same source, p. 267). In the discussion of this name, the author mentions that the name Sofia goes back to Muhammad, peace be upon him, in his explanation in the appendix, "It refers to the wife of our Prophet Muhammad (pbuh), Sophia, our mother." The mind of the reader goes back to the long history. In this place, the writer connects the genesis of reality even further. The fact that the novel is called "Genetic" and that its main character is an expert in this field is a separate matter. But the events coming from the couple of Aymomo and Aunt Sofia go back to a long history - to the times of Rasulullah (s.a.w.) and even further back. A geneticist is a scientist who studies human genes. In the plot line of the novel, there are episodes related to Aunt Sofia, a scientist in this field. The scientist's nephew examines a strand of his aunt Sofia's hair in a special laboratory. As a result, he comes across a very strange discovery, that is, he comes across "a treasure that boggles the mind of world scientists - the most unique and pure Eve gene in the universe." In the novel, the events of the scientist's youth require each other in the text of the work according to the category of cause and effect. In addition, the main purpose of the novel is to emphasize that the gene of the Uzbek people goes back to ancient times.

Isajon Sultan continued the traditions of Uzbek novelists in his own way in the updated conditions, at the same time, he creatively adopted the experiences of a number of representatives of world literature in the plot construction of his novels.

The list of used literature:

1. Damir Torayev. Poetics of the plot in contemporary Uzbek prose/Colorful images. Tashkent. "Akademnashr" publishing house. 2014, page 21
2. Tukhta Boboev. "Fundamentals of Literary Studies". Tashkent. "Teacher". 2002, page 217
3. Isajon Sultan. In the footsteps of Hazrat Khizr. Novels, short stories and stories. Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam. Tashkent. 2018. Page 258
4. Azimjon Rahimov. The art of the novel. "Fergana" publishing house. 2015, page 89.

⁵ Исажон Султон. Ҳазрати Хизр изидан. Роман, қисса ва ҳикоялар. Гафур Ғулом номидаги нашриёт-матбаа ижодий уйи. Тошкент. 2018. 266-бет.